

Influence of Rainfall Variability on Postharvest Technologies Adoption Among the Maize Farmers in Bungoma South Sub- County, Kenya

Catherine Nyongesa^{1*}, Dr. Joyce A. Obuoyo, (PhD)², Prof. Boniface O. Oindo, (PhD)³

^{1,2,3}School of Arts and Social Sciences, Department of Geography and Natural Resources Management, Maseno University, P. O. Box Private Bag, Maseno

ABSTRACT: Up to 30% of harvested maize is lost due to climate variability, which disrupts the drying process and creates conditions favourable for grain spoilage. Despite the availability of improved post-harvest storage technologies in the study area, their adoption remains low among maize farmers. Thus the aim of this research was to determine the influence of rainfall variability on post-harvest technologies adoption. A quasi-longitudinal research design was adopted for the study guided by Expected Utility and Diffusion theories. The unit of analysis was household maize farmers. The study encompassed the entire maize farming population of 32,137 households in Bungoma South Sub-County. Utilizing a systematic sampling technique, 400 respondents were selected from each ward, based on the proportionate share of maize farmers in each locality. The data collection was done using structured questionnaires. Secondary data was sourced from the Kenya Meteorological Departments' database and unpublished documents. Rainfall data was analyzed using Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis and regression analysis was used to estimate linear relationship between variations of rainfall on postharvest technologies adoption. The Mann-Kendall trend test results revealed statistically significant negative trends in annual rainfall ($S = -.856$, $p = 0.002$) and long rains ($S = -.924$, $p = 0.001$), with Sen's slopes of -8.5 mm/year and -9.2 mm/year respectively. In contrast, the trend for short rains was not statistically significant ($S = -.245$, $p = 0.125$), suggesting less consistent decline. However, the regression results revealed an R squared value of 0.96 indicating that 96% of the variation in the postharvest adoption of modern technologies among maize farmers was explained by rainfall variability. The study concluded that rainfall variability significantly influenced farmers' post-harvest storage technology choices. We recommend that farmers be guided by rainfall variability information when making choices on the most efficient, reliable and economical post-harvest technologies to use so as to reduce post-harvest losses during variable weather patterns, ultimately improving household food security.

KEYWORDS: Postharvest losses, rainfall variability, post-harvest storage technologies, post-harvest storage technology adoption, hermetic bags.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Globally, much of the climate-agriculture literature remained concentrated on rainfall impacts during the growing season affecting planting dates, crop yields, and drought tolerance (Kogo et al., 2021). While these studies were valuable, they overlooked the indirect but significant impact of rainfall variability on postharvest management, such as drying, handling, and storage. For instance, increased rainfall during harvest months lead to high grain moisture content, delayed drying, and increased risk of fungal contamination (FAO, 2020). Yet, postharvest phases are often treated as secondary, receiving minimal analytical attention in most climate impact studies.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, few studies have explicitly examined how total annual or seasonal rainfall fluctuations shape farmers' perceived need or urgency to adopt protective technologies like hermetic bags, solar dryers, or raised granaries. For example, Ambuko et al. (2021) documented the benefits of solar dryers in reducing weather-related spoilage, but did not explore whether adoption was driven by recent experiences of excessive or poorly timed rainfall. Similarly, Ogutu et al. (2023) discussed climate shocks broadly including rainfall extremes but often failed to disaggregate between rainfall-related production shocks and postharvest-stage disruptions. This lack of granularity limited the ability to understand whether specific rainfall trends were motivating farmers to adopt particular postharvest interventions.

Further, even where studies acknowledged climate variability, they often stopped short of examining how specific rainfall trends (e.g., intensity, timing, onset delays) influenced farmer behavior. Most used generalized climate indices or farmer recall data without validating rainfall trends through meteorological analysis. This methodological gap weakened the explanatory power of

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such studies. For instance, The Bungoma Development Plan 2019 states that variations in rainfall have a significant role in the 20–30% post-harvest losses that transpire within 6 months following harvest. Mugalavai et al (2008) in their research conquered with this and postulated that, the high variability of the commencement and end of the rainy season was the reason why rainfall features, such as the length of the growing, harvesting and drying seasons, have always been unknown. On the other, Wanjala et al. (2020) highlight that farmers perceive higher postharvest losses during erratic rainfall seasons, yet the study failed to quantify the relationship between rainfall data and technology uptake decisions.

While national and regional studies are useful, they often lack location-specific insights. Mugalavai et al (2008) in their study noted that Bungoma South Sub-County, with its unique agro-ecological zones and bimodal rainfall pattern, experiences localized postharvest challenges that may not be reflected in generalized data. Tefera, (2012), conducted some studies that essentially argued that some of the Bungoma County's current technologies for storing corn are so good that if they are adopted, a farmer does not

always need to introduce any additional preservation technique for the safety of the crops. One such example is the metal silos. However, few recent studies isolated sub-county level rainfall patterns or correlated them with micro-level technology adoption decisions, despite growing calls for climate adaptation strategies to be locally grounded (Muthoni et al., 2022).

Finally, there is also lack of intersectional analysis. While rainfall variability may be universal, its impacts on technology adoption are mediated by household resource levels, access to credit, labor availability, and gender roles. For example, female farmers may face more difficulty drying maize under erratic rainfall but also have less access to improved dryers or storage systems (Wanjala et al., 2020). Current studies rarely examine how rainfall variation interacts with socioeconomic status or institutional support to influence adoption.

In the study area, there is a lack of disaggregated data that links specific climate stressors (e.g., unseasonal rainfall, heatwaves) to farmers' postharvest decisions. The few available studies often generalized findings at the national level, overlooking localized climate experiences and the adaptive behavior of smallholder farmers. Studies carried out by Nchanji and Lutomia (2021) noted that increased rainfall variability during the harvesting season in parts of East Africa resulted in farmers being unable to properly dry maize, increasing mold and aflatoxin risk. Kumar and Kalita (2020) on the other hand pointed out that elevated humidity and temperature swings encouraged the proliferation of storage pests and fungal organisms, which caused quality and quantitative losses. Finally, Abass et al. (2022) observed that changes in seasonal rainfall patterns contributed to delays in harvesting, leading to higher field losses and subsequent postharvest storage spoilage in maize. While studies have examined storage innovations like hermetic bags, metal silos, and solar dryers, their performance under climate-induced stressors (e.g., variations in temperatures and rainfall) was underexplored, thereby creating a gap in evaluating the resilience of postharvest technologies with respect to annual seasonal temperature variations and the farmers' choice to either adopt the technologies or not.

Given the increasing unpredictability of weather patterns due to climate variability, it is crucial to understand how rainfall variability shapes farmer decisions regarding postharvest handling. Nampala et al. (2021) explored general barriers to technology adoption, often focusing on economic, educational, and institutional constraints. In a similar study, Affognon et al. (2020) identified cost, awareness, and access to credit as major factors influencing uptake of postharvest technologies in sub-Saharan Africa. Given that climate variability is a long-term phenomenon; postharvest studies should ideally employ longitudinal designs to detect evolving loss patterns that will be undertaken by this study. However, these studies revealed that there was limited empirical research examining the specific influence of short and long rainfall durations on postharvest technologies, a relationship that the current study intends to determine.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The study was carried out in Bungoma County. The nine Sub-Counties that make up the greater Bungoma County are Bungoma North, Bungoma South, Webuye East, Webuye West, Bungoma Central, Bungoma West, Kimilili, Mt. Elgon, and Bumula. Bungoma South Sub-County is one of those sub-counties. It is located between latitudes 00' 28 and 10' 30 north on longitude 34'30E. It shares borders with Bungoma Central Sub-County to the north, Webuye East Sub-County to the east, and Bumula Sub-County to the west. It has a total size of 329 square kilometers. There are 14 sub-locations and 5 administrative locations inside it. Kuywa, Nzoia, Sio, and Chwele are the rivers that supply water to the area and have permanent tributaries. The 2014 Bungoma County Strategic Plan

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Figure 2: Study Area

(Source: GOK, 2013)

3.3.2 Climate of the Study Area

Climate of the Study Area

Bungoma South experiences dependable yearly rainfall in the range of 1000 mm to 1500 mm, with a bimodal pattern consisting of long rains from March to July and short rains from August to October. December, January, and February are often the months with the least amount of rainfall. The sub-County is located in the Lake Victoria Basin, with annual temperatures ranging from 21 to 25°C and elevations between 1200 and 1500 meters above sea level (A.S.L.) (GoK, 2013). The majority of farmers in the county are depended on the unpredictable and irregular rains. Low crop yields and post-harvest losses are partly caused by an increase in pest and disease events brought on by rainfall and temperature variations (County Government of Bungoma 2021).

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research design

The study adopted a quasi- longitudinal research design. This was because data on postharvest maize technologies adoption was collected from farmers and key informants at the point in time when the study was conducted and described to depict the influence that climate variability had on post-harvest maize technologies adoption among farmers. This data collected was important especially in the analysis of objective one. However, in addition to that, the 37 year rainfall and temperature data was also sought from the KMD database for over the period 1987-2024. This data formed part of an already existing information in relation to this study but was key in generating information that enabled the researcher investigate the variations in annual mean temperature and rainfall over the 37years hence the analysis of objectives 2,3&4.

Study Population and Sampling Procedure

Sample size

The sample size was determined using the Yamane (1973) algorithm at a desired level of precision was 5%. This formula was deemed suitable as a result of the large population in the study area.

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + N)e^2}$$

n = Sample size, N=Total size of the population and e = level of significance $\alpha= 0.05$.

$$n = \frac{32,137}{(1+32,137) 0.05^2}$$

n=400 maize farmers

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Sampling Techniques

The sampling frame for the study included all maize farmers in Bungoma South Sub-County which is 32137 (Bungoma County Development Plan 2017-2022). Using Yamane (1973) the sample size was calculated to approximately 400. Systematic sampling technique was used to select the maize farmers. Using the a above sample determination formula, 400 sample respondents were picked at random from each ward using a systematic random sampling technique, with the selection process based on probability proportionate to size. However, purposive sampling was used to select key informants where one senior officer from the MOA and KMD were approached respectively. Their percentage to the overall share of households in each ward was used to calculate the sample size from each ward.

Table 3.1: Sample Households to be selected for the Study

Wards	Population	Proportion	Sample size
1. Tuuti Marakaru	3021	0.094	37
2. Khalaba	2058	0.064	26
3. Township	65	0.002	1
4. Musikoma	5463	0.17	68
5. Bukembe East	4821	0.15	60
6. Bukembe West	4177	0.13	52
7. West Sang'alo	6748	0.21	84
8. East Sang'alo	5784	0.18	72
	32,137		

Source: Author's compilation, 2024

DATA COLLECTION

Primary Data

The study used a structured questionnaire as a data collection tool to collect the primary data. The questionnaire gathered information on types of Postharvest technologies used (traditional & modern) in Bungoma South Sub-County. The structured questionnaires utilized closed and open- ended questions covering all the areas of study.

Focus Group Discussions (FGD)

The process of administering the survey also involved recruiting the focus group discussants. Potential focus group discussion participants were notified about a follow-up study during data collection, and they were asked whether they would be willing to participate. Focus group sessions extracted people's thoughts and feelings regarding local viewpoints in a setting that allowed them to explore the manner in which goods or services directly impacted them (Flachs, 2019).

According to Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003, at least 10-30% of the accessible population is viable and representative enough to yield acceptable and reliable results for a generalization. Therefore, in total, 32 discussants participated in three focus groups that were deliberately chosen from the wider group of survey participants.

Respondents were represented by three of the eight surveyed wards in the Sub-county: Township (5 discussants), Bukembe (12 discussants), and Sang'alo (15 discussants) proportional to the sample size derived from each ward. The selection process for participants included a range of perspectives, and experience in growing and storing maize. The research questions served as a guide for the focus group talks, which run roughly an hour in each case. The participant selection was aimed at obtaining varying viewpoints, gender representativeness, and maize farming & storage experience. The discussions provided a cross sectional perspective of farmers' experiences with and views of post- harvest maize storage technology use in their homes. The conversations contributed to the production of detailed information regarding some survey results and farmer perspectives that might not have been sufficiently gathered by the semi-structured questionnaires. The identical research questions were used in each focus group to maintain uniformity.

Table 3.2 Focus Group Discussant Breakdown

Ward	Number of Discussants
Township(township,khalaba& musikoma	5
Bukembe(East&West)	12
Sang'alo(East&	15

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(West)

Key informant interviews

Data on climate variables was also captured using in-depth interviews from key informants (officers from the KMD) for the last thirty-seven years' worth of records, which stretched from 1987 to 2024. Similarly, officers from the MOA were also interviewed on PHST adoption using the interview guide questions.

3.5.2 Secondary Data

Daily data for rainfall was obtained from the KMD for the period 1987-2024 so as to calculate the total mean annual rainfall variations for Bungoma South Sub-County. The rainfall figures for the Sub County were recorded in a summary check sheet. Table: 3.3 below indicate the instruments that were employed and the target data collected.

Table 3.3: Data Collection Instruments, Variable and Sources

Variable	Data required	Source of data	Data type	Data collection Instruments
Rainfall	Total annual mean rainfall	KMD	Secondary	Summary check Sheet
Maize postharvest technologies adoption	Types of Postharvest technologies used (traditional & modern)	House hold heads among the maize farmers in Bungoma South Sub-County -Officers(MOA)	Primary	-Questionnaires -FGD

3.6 Data Analysis and Results Presentation

- i) Rainfall data was analyzed using Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis to examine possible trends over the 37-year period under consideration.
- ii) A regression analysis was used to estimate linear relationship between variations of rainfall on postharvest technologies adoption

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Influence of Total Annual Seasonal Rainfall Variations on Post-harvest Technologies Adoption

Rainfall patterns and Trends (1987-2024)

In order to establish the rainfall trends and variations over the 37-year period under study, the Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis (table 3.4) were done based on the rainfall data from the KMD.

Table 3.4: Mann-Kendall Trend Test Results for rainfall trends;

Parameter	Test Statistic (S)	p-value	Sen's Slope
Annual Rainfall	-.856	0.002*	-8.5
Long Ra ins	-.924	0.001*	-9.2
Short Rains	-.245	0.125	-1.8
Rainy Days	-.785	0.003*	-0.7
Dry Spells	+.658	0.008*	+0.2
*Significant at p < 0.05			

The Mann-Kendall trend test results revealed statistically significant negative trends in annual rainfall ($S = -.856$, $p = 0.002$) and long rains ($S = -.924$, $p = 0.001$), with Sen's slopes of -8.5 mm/year and -9.2 mm/year respectively (Table 4.10d). This confirmed a long-term decline in total rainfall, particularly during the main cropping season. In contrast, the trend for short rains was not statistically significant ($S = -.245$, $p = 0.125$), suggesting less consistent decline. Additionally, the number of rainy days also decreased significantly ($S = -.785$, $p = 0.003$, slope = -0.7 days/year), while dry spells increased significantly ($S = +.658$, $p = 0.008$), with a slope of $+0.2$ days/year. These results implied worsening intra-seasonal rainfall distribution, with both reduced frequency and amount of rainfall, and more prolonged dry periods.

The observed declines in rainfall and increases in dry spells heightened the risk of improper maize drying, increased pest infestation, and aflatoxin contamination, directly influencing farmers' adoption of adaptive storage technologies (Tefera et al.,

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2011; Affognon, Mutungi, Sanginga, & Borgemeister, 2015). From the perspective of Expected Utility Theory (EUT), these trends increased the perceived expected losses from non-adoption, motivating farmers to implement hermetic bags, metal silos, and other protective storage measures (Feder, Just, & Zilberman, 1985; Deressa, Hassan, Ringler, Alemu, & Yesuf, 2009). Farmers thus made risk-informed decisions, balancing the cost of technology adoption against potential postharvest losses. In addition to that, according to Diffusion of Innovation Theory, early adopters of postharvest technologies influenced broader community adoption through demonstration and observation (Rogers, 2003; Pretty, Toulmin, & Williams, 2011). The Mann-Kendall results suggested that farmers were increasingly aware of rainfall variability, which acted as a trigger for adoption and information-sharing. Communities experiencing visible losses during declining rainfall periods were more likely to adopt new storage technologies more rapidly as the relative advantages became apparent (Birner et al., 2009; Tefera et al., 2011).

Regression analysis between total annual seasonal rainfall variations and postharvest technologies adoption

A regression analysis was conducted to predict the influence of rainfall variability on postharvest technologies adoption among the maize farmers in the Sub-County. The results of the model summary were presented in tables 3.5.

3.5: Model Summary of Simple linear regression results of Rainfall Variability and Postharvest Technology Adoption

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Sig. Change	F
					Change	F Change	df1	df2		
1	.961 ^a	.923	.906	.29435	.923	54.172	2	9	.000	

a. Predictors: (Constant), Long rainfall coefficient of variation, Short rainfall coefficient of variation

b. Dependent Variable: Adopted technology

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-10.424	3.029			-3.442	.007
	Short rainfall coefficient of variation	-1.350	.623	-.1560		-2.168	.058
	Long rainfall coefficient of variation	1.370	.396	.2487		3.456	.007

a. Dependent Variable: Adopted technology

The regression results revealed an R squared value of 0.96 indicating that 96% of the variation in the postharvest adoption of modern technologies among maize farmers was explained by rainfall variability. Only 4% of their adoption behavior was due other factors (like cost, awareness, extension services). This demonstrated that rainfall unpredictability was a major determinant of technology uptake in Bungoma South Sub- County. The entire model was extremely relevant ($F(2,9) = 54.172, p < .001$), which attested to the strength of the explanatory force.

In addition to that, the regression coefficients indicated distinct effects for long and short rains: Firstly, long rainfall coefficient of variation had a positive and significant effect on technology adoption ($B = 1.370, t = 3.456, p = 0.007$). This suggested that as variability in long rains increased, farmers were more likely to adopt adaptive postharvest technologies such as hermetic storage, metal silos, and improved drying platforms. The positive relationship was consistent with the expectation that greater unpredictability in the main rainy season increased the risk of maize losses, thus motivating adoption (Tefera et al., 2011; Affognon et al., 2015).

On the other hand, short rainfall coefficient of variation showed a negative effect ($B = -1.350, t = -2.168, p = 0.058$), which was marginally non-significant at the 5% level. This indicated that variability in short rains did not strongly influence farmers' adoption behavior, possibly because short rains contributed less to maize growth or drying periods in the study area (Porter et al., 2014; Martey, Kuwornu, & Anang, 2012). Finally, the constant term ($-10.424, p = 0.007$) represented the baseline adoption level when rainfall variability was zero, suggesting that in the absence of variability, adoption rates were minimal.

The coefficient equation used to generate the regression equation was as follows: **Adopted Technology = -10.424 - 1.350(Short Rainfall CV) + 1.370(Long Rainfall CV)**

The constant (**10.424**) meant that if both short rainfall variability and long rainfall variability were zero (perfectly stable rainfall) the baseline level of adoption of postharvest technologies would be 10.424 units. This implied that even without rainfall variability, farmers already adopted some basic postharvest technologies probably due to awareness created by extension officers; need to reduce pests, cultural practice of storing maize, postharvest market requirements among others. Therefore rainfall

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variability added to this baseline, but farmers did not start from zero. The coefficient for short rainfall variability was negative (-1.350), implying that an increase in variability during the short rains was associated with a decrease in adoption of postharvest technologies. This was attributed to the fact that the short rains constituted a secondary production season; therefore, higher variability reduced maize output and consequently lowered farmers motivation or capacity to adopt technologies during this period.

In contrast, the coefficient for long rainfall variability was positive and statistically stronger (+1.370). This suggested that increase in variability during the long rains lead to higher adoption of postharvest technologies. Since the Long rains formed the main maize production period, unpredictability during this period exposed farmers to significant postharvest risks such as high grain moisture, mold development and aflatoxin contamination. As a result, farmers responded by increasing uptake of technologies such as hermetic storage improved drying systems, and moisture control devices to protect their harvests. Overall, the coefficients confirm that rainfall variability- especially during the long rains was a major determinant of postharvest technology adoption in the study area.

From the EUT perspective, farmers made adoption decisions based on risk and expected benefits (Feder, Just, & Zilberman, 1985; Adesina & Zinnah, 1993). The positive coefficient for long rain variability reflected risk-driven decision-making: higher variability increased the expected postharvest losses, raising the utility of adopting protective technologies. This aligned with prior studies showing that farmers responded to climatic uncertainty by adopting risk-reducing interventions (Deressa, Hassan, Ringler, Alemu, & Yesuf, 2009; Fosu-Mensah, Vlek, & MacCarthy, 2012).

The marginal negative effect of short rain variability indicated that farmers weighed the relative expected loss differently for short rains, which had less impact on drying and storage conditions, highlighting the nuanced decision-making process predicted by EUT (Lobell, Schlenker, & Costa-Roberts, 2011; Maddison, 2007).

Similarly, the regression results also support the DOI framework, which argued that adoption was influenced by perceived relative advantage, observability, and social influence (Rogers, 2003; Pretty, Toulmin, & Williams, 2011). As long rain variability became more noticeable, early adopters implemented technologies that reduced postharvest losses, serving as models for peers. This process accelerated adoption within the farming community, creating community-wide uptake in response to climatic stress (Birner et al., 2009; Tefera et al., 2011).

5.0 CONCLUSION

The findings of this study demonstrated that the Mann-Kendall trend test results revealed statistically significant negative trends in annual rainfall ($S = -.856$, $p = 0.002$) and long rains ($S = -.924$, $p = 0.001$), with Sen's slopes of -8.5 mm/year and -9.2 mm/year respectively (Table 4.9). In contrast, the trend for short rains was not statistically significant ($S = -.245$, $p = 0.125$), suggesting less consistent decline. Further analysis revealed a significant decline in annual rainfall (40% reduction from 1987 to 2024). Long rains showed more pronounced changes (-39.7%) compared to short rains (+1.1%). The results therefore implied worsening intra-seasonal rainfall distribution, with both reduced frequency and amount of rainfall, and more prolonged dry periods. However, the regression results (Table 3.5) revealed an R squared value of 0.96 indicating that 96% of the variation in the postharvest adoption of modern technologies among maize farmers was explained by rainfall variability. Therefore it was concluded that rainfall variations had high influence on farmers' post-harvest technologies adoption decisions.

6.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Maize farmers should be guided by information on variations of rainfall when making choices on the most efficient, reliable and economical post-harvest technologies to adopt so as to reduce post-harvest losses during unpredictable weather patterns.

Suggestions for Further Research

The following areas are recommended for future research:

1. Long-term studies on the durability and effectiveness of modern storage technologies under different climate scenarios
2. Explore how farmers' perceptions of these rainfall components interact with socio-economic variables to influence technology adoption, with a focus on scaling climate-resilient postharvest solutions

Competing interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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